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“FROM SETBACKS TO SUCCESS: A JOURNEY OF LEARNING, NAVIGATION, HOPE AND SUCCESS”

Today is not just a celebration of accomplishments, it is a celebration of journeys. Each of you sitting here has overcome your own challenges and celebrated your triumphs to arrive at this milestone.

For me, being here is also a full-circle moment.

Back in 2016, I had the privilege of serving Libhu National High School as one of the pioneer teachers of the DepEd Senior High School program. It was an exciting time, especially knowing that this school had already gained recognition as one of the best in Maasin City—championing sports, journalism, and a wide range of academic and extracurricular pursuits.

Inspired by the school’s reputation, I made a promise to myself: I would dedicate my efforts to propel Libhu NHS to even greater heights. Together with my colleagues, we worked tirelessly—overcoming shortcomings, failures, miscommunications, and even unfulfilled plans. We persevered to ensure that the school would become a home for resilient, dedicated, and competent learners.

Now, almost a decade later, standing here before you, I see the fruits of those efforts. Libhu NHS has sustained its place as a competitive school, producing graduates who are not only prepared but hungry to embark on their new academic and professional journeys. This is a testament to the spirit of this school and its community—a spirit of perseverance, growth, and excellence.

It is with great humility and joy that I share my story with you, hoping it serves as a reflection of resilience and inspiration. I have structured my message to you today around the acronym LNHS—a journey that mirrors my own path in life.

Let’s begin with the first letter, L which stands for LEARN

Many people recognize my success, but few know the journey behind it. Back in college, I wasn’t able to graduate on time. Yes, I was delayed by a semester because of our unapproved thesis. The university I attended was strict with deadlines, and as a graduating student, the pressure was overwhelming—graduation requirements, on-the-job training, final exams, term papers, laboratory reports, symposiums—all of it piling up at once.

In our thesis group of three, we struggled to meet the deadline. When we learned we wouldn't be graduating on time, we lost the drive to finish. Our friendship even suffered as we blamed one another for our failure. But eventually, we realized that pointing fingers would get us nowhere, least of all to the finish line. It felt like carrying the weight of the world.

The hardest part was telling my parents. They were so excited about my graduation, and I dreaded their reaction to the news. I confided first in my elder sister, breaking down in tears and feeling immense pity for myself. She helped me by talking to our parents on my behalf. In my heart, I feared their disappointment, but to my surprise, they met me with deep understanding. They never made me feel like a failure.

On the day of what should have been my graduation, I traveled back home, consumed by realizations and "what-ifs." Yet, home became my sanctuary. My family gave me the comfort and healing I desperately needed, showing me that failure wasn't the end. Instead, they uplifted, motivated, and restored my hope.

A month after graduation, my thesis partners regrouped with a renewed sense of determination. Our adviser's support and encouragement inspired us to push forward. We successfully defended our thesis, and one of my groupmates even submitted it for publication. To our delight, it was accepted. A sweet ending indeed.

From this experience, I realized that life is a constant teacher, and its lessons often come disguised as failures. But failure isn't the opposite of success—it's part of it. Each failure teaches us something new: perseverance, humility, and growth. No matter how hard the lesson, there's always wisdom to be gained if we choose to learn from it.

The second letter is N, for NAVIGATE.

The road of life isn't straight—it twists, it turns, and sometimes, it makes us feel completely lost. I've faced crossroads many times, including right after I graduated from college.

Since elementary school, whenever I was asked about my ambition in life, I always had the same answer: "to become a doctor." That dream led me to specialize in Biology, as it provided a strong foundation for medical school. Before graduation, most of my classmates, including me, took the National Medical Admission Test. We were thrilled with our results and even received scholarship opportunities—though these were for schools outside Cebu. Still, the results qualified us for medical schools within Cebu, but without scholarships.

Excited, I shared the good news with my parents, handing them the letter with pride. But to my surprise, they candidly told me they couldn't afford to send me to medical school. I was shocked and unsure how to react. I tried to compose myself, knowing how supportive they had always been of my dreams. I understood the financial burden medical school entailed, yet I felt disappointed and hurt. I couldn't help but think they could have told me earlier, so I could have sought other opportunities or scholarships.

During dinner that evening, I let my frustration get the better of me. I walked away from the table without finishing my meal—an act I now recognize as disrespectful. A few days later, my parents sat me down to discuss alternatives. They encouraged me to pursue another career where my degree would still be valuable. They suggested I earn education units, but I declined. Instead, I decided to return to Cebu and look for a job.

Job hunting was far from easy. It made me realize how much simpler it seemed to be a student compared to searching for work. I submitted countless applications, attended interviews, and faced rejection after rejection. It was exhausting and disheartening.

Eventually, I applied for a position teaching English to Korean students, which was a popular job in Cebu at the time. To my surprise, I got accepted. I went through the training process and was even recognized as the best trainee in my batch. That recognition motivated me to give my best and remain dedicated to my work. Right after the camp or term, my manager offered me a contract renewal, but I declined.

I went home and revisited my parents' earlier suggestion to pursue education. They were overjoyed and supportive of my decision. I enrolled to earn teaching units, and here's the twist: the same institution where I was studying offered me a part-time teaching position for afternoon classes while I attended daytime sessions as a unit earner. It made me question, "Am I really destined to become a teacher?"

Though I was still unsure of my path, I came to an important realization: I needed to trust myself. I was charting my own path, but I also acknowledged that God had other plans—bigger plans than I could imagine.

From aspiring medical doctor to destined educator, I learned that what matters most is acceptance. Acceptance lightens burdens, helps us come to terms with harsh realities, and ultimately sets us free. Redirection is part of life's journey. Navigating through life is never a smooth road, but with purpose and determination, we eventually find our way despite the obstacles.

Then we come to H, which means HOPE.

Hope is the light that guides us through the darkness. There were times when I felt like giving up, but holding onto hope kept me moving forward. I have faced many dark moments, but two stand out as my deepest challenges.

The first was when I was about to finish my education units. Teaching had become a fulfilling passion for me. Day by day, I grew more excited about the learning experiences it brought—listening to colleagues, engaging with students, and developing myself as an educator. I felt that I had partially answered the calling of being a teacher, but I was eager to take the next step: earning my teaching license.

Graduation was scheduled for the last week of March 2013, and only my mother and brother attended because my father was gravely ill and stayed home with my sister. It was a bittersweet moment. While I celebrated this milestone, just a few days later, on April 9, my father passed away. We were thrust into complete darkness. What should have been a time of triumph was overshadowed by sorrow.

Losing my father derailed my focus and made me question the path ahead. But I remembered the promise I had made—not to let this opportunity slip away, especially since my dream of becoming a medical doctor was no longer within reach. I stumbled and do not have the perseverance to get back but I saw hope in the eyes of my family, my classmates in education and my supervisors who have faith in me—to become a successful full-fledged teacher. I resigned from being a part time instructor, and focused on my self-review.

We took the exam in September with high hopes of getting a passing percentage. Two months after, the result was released however Yolanda devastated the region and the access of getting the result was a challenge. My sister that time was in Bohol and she was the first to inform me that I passed the board exam.

I was happy. I was even happier that my other classmates made it. And I was one of the happiest when we later knew that our Batch garnered a 100% passing rate. We brought pride to our institution; we were honored and I have ended my journey in getting the education license as a speaker during the honoring ceremony. I could not help but got tears in my eyes as I delivered my speech, highlighting the bright and dark moments of my life and on how I went through. Indeed, there's a light at the very end of the tunnel.

The second nightmare was when I pursued for my doctoral degree. This was the time pandemic hit but I cannot completely consider pandemic as an obstacle. In fact, we were privileged to continue learning from the comfort of our homes, submit academic requirements and enroll online and even take the comprehensive exam at home.

Not until I was diagnosed with a gall bladder stone. The moment the probe touched my abdomen and was able to detect a foreign object, everything darkened. The diagnosis felt like the earth crumbling beneath me. I can't believe to have this ailment, despite of the measures I have applied to keep my body healthy. Again, I was lost and demotivated. The pain was relentless, and painkillers provided little relief.

There are times when I go to work restless and even complete my doctoral requirements without focus, and just simply for compliance. I endured the condition for about a year because of my fear of undergoing surgery. It was never easy.

In June 2022, I fainted at work. My skin and eyes had turned yellow—an alarming sign that the condition had worsened. Accompanied by my mother and brother, I sought expert medical advice. While surgery was deemed urgent, I begged the doctor to allow me to defend my dissertation first. He reluctantly agreed but warned of potential complications. I prayed to God that this would be put into place at the right time. I cried, and I have difficulty getting rest.

I talked to my dissertation adviser about my condition, and he was shocked. He even advised that the defense would be done after my surgery, but I insisted. I know that this will be risky, and he is just after of my health, just like others. He helped me arrange with the schedule, and the panelists were eager as well to attend as soon as possible. June 16, I defended my dissertation, and it was accepted with minor revisions. But the following day, I was admitted. A series of medical clearings were performed, and thank God, there have been no complications. The next day, the gallstones were removed from my body successfully.

I stayed in the hospital for a few days with so much gratitude to God for accompanying me in this very dark moment of life, for putting everything into place, and for sending people who acted as instruments of hope and healing.

Through these challenges, I realized that hope has the power to rekindle our spirits and remind us that tomorrow brings new opportunities, even amid uncertainty. Hope is a collective force—found in the eyes of others, in difficult situations, and in the support we receive. Truly, hope has the ability to turn setbacks into stepping stones.

And now we arrive to the last letter of LNHS. S, which stands for SUCCEED.

Success isn't about avoiding failures—it's about facing them, learning from them, and pushing forward. Every achievement I have celebrated was built on resilience, hard work, and belief in myself. Who would have thought that someone who couldn't graduate on time because of an unapproved thesis is now leading the

Office of Research and Development of a university? Who would have thought that someone who once dreamed of being a medical doctor would earn a doctorate in education and become passionate about shaping and molding the future of this generation?

Yes, I strongly believe that dreams provide us with direction, but it is important to note that it takes courage and determination to get to the finish line, to the pinnacle of success. We need to go through a process: we need to experience pain to truly appreciate healing, we shed tears to understand joy, and we face failure to fully value success.

Remember, success looks different for everyone. Define your own version of success, and don't be afraid to pursue it with passion.

